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SOLID PANCREATIC TUMORS

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Pancreatic tumors represent a heterogeneous group of tumors of different histological origin and different malignant potential. However, ductal adenocarcinoma poses the greatest clinical relevance, being the fourth leading cause of cancer mortality in European countries. On the other hand, neuroendocrine tumors encounter for the second most common solid pancreatic tumors, again with different malignant potential, and different clinical and imaging pattern.

The early diagnosis of pancreatic tumors is difficult, for the clinical symptoms are usually absent, non-specific and slowly progressive, and they are often incidentally found on imaging studies. If located in the head, which accounts for approximately 60-70% of the cases of pancreatic cancer, they present earlier than in the body or tail, by obstructive jaundice. In body or tail tumors, first clinical symptoms are due to the mass effect, invasion of adjacent structures or malignant tumor/paraneoplastic syndrome, thus signs may include abdominal pain, weight loss, nausea, fatigue, steatorrhea, new-onset diabetes, venous thrombosis and/or migratory thrombophlebitis, with palpable abdominal mass, hepatomegaly and ascites in advanced stage.

Transabdominal ultrasound (US) is the first line imaging modality for patients presenting with jaundice or abdominal pain, and the presence of the most of the tumors is confirmed with this study. Computed tomography (CT) is the mostly used imaging method for characterization of solid pancreatic lesions and evaluation of tumor extension and tumor burden. Endoscopic ultrasound (EUS) with its excellent visualization of the pancreas offers added value in further characterization of lesions and in local staging, with the great advantage of fine needle aspiration biopsy (FNAB).

If the pancreatic mass is resectable according to the CT finding, prior to surgery EUS is preferred to confirm the local stage, especially relation to the vascular structures. Borderline resectable lesions and locally advanced disease require EUS with FNAB confirmation. In metastatic disease, biopsy of the metastasis, usually liver metastasis, confirm the diagnosis.

While magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has similar performance in the presurgical evaluation of pancreatic cancer compared to CT, MRI adds specificity in tissue characterization and is proven to be better for characterization of cystic pancreatic lesions. Magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography (MRCP) allows noninvasive visualization of pancreatic and biliary ductal system, and currently endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) is considered when ductal interventions are needed.

Differential diagnosis to various forms of chronic pancreatitis can be challenging, it is linked with the similarity of the tissue composition, and therefore similar imaging presentation. Chronic pancreatitis is the risk factor for pancreatic cancer, and on the other hand pancreatic duct obstruction can cause pancreatic inflammation upstream. There are numerous papers offering signs to distinguish the two entities, including shape of the lesion, intrinsic tissue characteristics, type of duct stenosis/dilatation, ADC values and others, but close follow up or biopsy is usually needed.

In this lecture, different solid tumors and their imaging characteristics, diagnostic workup of malignant solid tumors and differentiation to chronic pancreatitis will be discussed.